

1 **Tribological behaviour of additively manufactured Ti6Al4V with controlled surface structure:**
2 **An application in small joint implants**

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11
12 ***Abstract***

13 This study conducts a tribological analysis of Ti6Al4V samples with surface structure
14 manufactured by 3D printing to evaluate their suitability as friction pairs in joint replacements. The
15 behaviour was analysed using a tribometer with a pin-on-plate configuration, under conditions
16 simulating those typically observed in vivo. The grid structure outperformed other samples: while
17 exhibiting comparable friction to a homogeneous surface, it was the only one with the ability to retain
18 albumin present in contact and successfully restored the lubrication film after the unloading phase.
19 However, findings suggest that further refinements are needed before the structure can be considered fit
20 for application. The preliminary results indicate a need for greater proximity and regularity in the
21 structures.

22
23 ***Keywords***

24 3D printing of joint implants; Ti6Al4V alloy; Lubrication mechanism; Friction

25 ***1. Introduction***

26 In the contemporary world, where individuals are striving to maintain an active lifestyle even at
27 an advanced age, and where there are numerous cases of injury, the research and development of joint
28 replacements represents an indispensable component of healthcare. Further advances may be made in
29 the design of new types of joint replacement or the search for more suitable friction surfaces. The number
30 of joint replacements performed is increasing on an annual basis [1]. Nevertheless, the current generation
31 of implants is not yet optimally developed for certain joints, necessitating early revision, which is highly
32 undesirable. One joint where the utilisation of joint implants is less prevalent than that of the second
33 possible intervention (arthrodesis) is the first metatarsophalangeal (1. MTP) joint of the big toe [2]. This
34 is primarily due to the limited lifespan of these implants, which is attributed to high rates of osteolysis,
35 subsidence, and implant failure, necessitating revision surgery. It is noteworthy that the revision rate for
36 this specific joint is relatively high [3].

37 In terms of design, a variety of alternative replacement types are produced for this specific joint,
38 typically comprising metallic and polymeric components. The metallic material most commonly utilised
39 for the friction pair is CoCrMo alloy. However, in other components of the implant, Ti6Al4V alloy is
40 often used to secure it to the bone [4,5] due to its material properties, which are more similar to those of
41 human bone, thus facilitating the desired osteointegration [6]. In recent years, 3D printing has emerged
42 as a prominent technology across all fields of manufacturing. This trend is also evident in the field of
43 joint replacements [7,8], where the most commonly utilised material is the aforementioned Ti6Al4V
44 alloy [9]. In the context of 3D metal printing, a number of possible methods have been identified [9],
45 including nanoparticle jetting, binder jetting, powder bed fusion, and directed energy deposition. Of
46 these methods, powder bed fusion is the most prevalent. The primary benefit of additive manufacturing
47 is demonstrated in several studies [10,11] which indicate that the wear can be notably reduced through
48 the use of additive manufacturing in comparison to conventional casting methods.

49 The lubrication mechanism of joint replacements is a highly complex problem, as the joints are
50 lubricated by synovial fluid (bovine calf serum in certain laboratory experiments), which is a highly
51 complex non-Newtonian fluid [12] and also contains proteins that may behave differently under certain
52 conditions [13]. Myant et al. [14] proposed a novel lubrication mechanism, named Protein Aggregation

53 Lubrication (PAL), which is applicable to contact pairs lubricated by synovial fluid or any kind of
54 lubricant containing proteins. This mechanism is based on the formation of a high-viscosity reservoir in
55 the inlet zone. The reservoir is principally the consequence of shear aggregation of protein molecules
56 within the inlet flow field. Subsequently, this lubrication mechanism was also described using an
57 analytical model by Nissim et al. [15], which demonstrated that the mechanism can be modelled using
58 classical elasto-hydrodynamic lubrication theory, supplemented by a protein concentration-dependent
59 constitutive equation for fluid viscosity. It has been demonstrated that certain dependencies exist with
60 regard to the behaviour of synovial fluid. It is evident that proteins form specific layers that facilitate an
61 overall lubrication mechanism [16,17].

62 The application of surface texturing has been demonstrated across a wide range of machine
63 components. This includes the field of human joint replacements, where it has been proved that textures
64 can perform four potential functions. These functions are as follows: acting as reservoirs for lubricant,
65 providing space for the accumulation of debris generated by wear, functioning as micro-hydrodynamic
66 bearings, and reducing the nominal contact area [18]. These effects collectively contribute to a reduction
67 in the overall wear rate, which represents a primary objective in the field of joint replacements, as the
68 ability of the prosthesis to last as long as possible in the patient's body is the main goal. A variety of
69 shapes, depths and layouts [18,19] were evaluated in terms of their suitability for use. It has been
70 demonstrated that the utilisation of textures in the contact area may serve to increase the coefficient of
71 friction (CoF). Nevertheless, the results of the long-term testing indicate that there is a positive effect
72 on durability, as it was demonstrated that the microstructures are capable of trapping hard wear particles
73 [20], which do not further contribute to secondary wear. Surface texturing of joint implants showed
74 positive behaviour in the context of reversal sliding motion [21], which is characteristic of human
75 movement during typical walking activities, by quick decrease in coefficient of friction. Shen et al. [20]
76 showed that textures with sharp corners are not the optimal choice for human joint implants, as it leads
77 to interlocking phenomenon. The authors subsequently assigned a ranking to the texture parameters,
78 identifying the following as the most influential: area density, size, geometry, depth and distribution
79 mode. The existing literature on the subject of dimple-shaped textures is replete with discussion of their
80 behaviour, which can be characterised as affecting the pressure distribution in the contact area and

81 changing the thickness of the lubricating film at the dimple interface [22]. An increase in thickness was
82 observed at the rear end, while conversely a decrease in thickness was noted at the sides and front in
83 direction of passing through the contact area.

84 This paper builds upon our previous research [23], which demonstrated that the behaviour of
85 the Ti6Al4V alloy is not entirely optimal. Nevertheless, the material can be used in the manufacture of
86 small joint replacements, provided that the surface of the specimen undergoes some form of
87 modification. The decision was taken to employ 3D printing technology to create structures on the
88 sample surface for the purposes of this research, with the objective of answering the following question:
89 *“What is the effect of a controlled surface structure on the tribological behaviour of the friction surface*
90 *of an additively manufactured Ti6Al4V alloy?”* To address this question, the research focused on the
91 description of lubrication film thickness, the development of constituents contained in the synovial fluid,
92 as well as the analysis of friction and the analysis of the wear after the experiments. These observed
93 parameters obtained for the structured samples were then compared with those obtained for the samples
94 with a homogenous surface in order to ascertain the differences in their tribological behaviour.

96 **2. Materials and Methods**

97 The study involved experiments on a tribometer (schematically depicted in Fig. 1) with a
98 pin-on-plate configuration that allowed reciprocal motion [17,23,24]. Moreover, the simulator employed
99 permits the simultaneous measurement of the coefficient of friction and observation of the contact area
100 due to its construction.

101

102 **Fig. 1** Tribometer with pin-on-plate configuration.

103 The experiments were primarily designed to describe the thickness of the lubrication film and its
 104 development. Two optical observation methods were employed, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The primary
 105 methodology employed was colorimetric interferometry [25], which was augmented by fluorescent
 106 microscopy [26] in order to gain insight into the behaviour of protein albumin within the contact area.
 107 As previously noted, the simulator enables simultaneous measurement of the friction coefficient and
 108 observation of the contact area with these observation methods, thereby enabling an appropriate
 109 correlation of these results.

110
 111 *Fig. 2 Schemes of optical methods: Colorimetric interferometry (left) and Fluorescent microscopy (right).*

112
 113 **Contact Pair and Lubricant**

114 The experimental contact pair consisted of pins manufactured from the Ti6Al4V alloy and the B270
 115 glass. The glass component was a necessary component for enabling observation of the contact area
 116 using optical methods. Furthermore, the glass employed in experiments conducted with the use of
 117 colorimetric interferometry was coated with chromium and an anti-reflective layer, thereby enhancing
 118 its functionality. The pins were manufactured using Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) technology from
 119 Ti6Al4V Grade 23 powder, which meets the ASTM F3001 specification. The SLM 280 HL 3D printer
 120 from Nikon SLM Solutions AG was used, which is equipped with a near-infrared ytterbium fibre laser
 121 with a maximum power of 700 W and a beam diameter of 82 μm , exhibiting a Gaussian power
 122 distribution. The L-PBF samples were fabricated with a layer thickness of 30 μm and under an inert gas
 123 (argon) with a maximum oxygen concentration of 0.05%. In total, three variants of the pin were

124 produced, each with a diameter of 9.8 mm and height of 12 mm. The first variant was produced with a
125 homogeneous surface, whereas the second and third variants were manufactured with a surface structure
126 designed to simulate texturing, created directly during the 3D printing process. The second and third
127 types of pins had a structure based on the meander printing strategy with a rotation of either 0° or 90°
128 in each layer, respectively (see Fig. 3). The process parameters for the creation of the structures were
129 set as follows: hatch distance 0.179 mm, laser power 100 W, and laser speed 450 mm/s. The surface
130 structure was created at a height of 2 mm. In order to conduct the experiments, the surface of each pin
131 was ground and polished to a curvature radius of 100 mm and surface roughness (with masked
132 structures) of $R_a = 40 \pm 10$ nm. The samples were not subjected to a heat treatment process as Khun [27]
133 showed that such a process does not significantly impact the wear rate of the 3D printed Ti6Al4V, on
134 the contrary, deterioration may occur at elevated temperatures.

135 The contact pair was flooded with a model synovial fluid (M-SF) that had been prepared
136 synthetically and which corresponded in composition to the SF extracted from patients who had
137 undergone arthroplasty [28]. The composition of the M-SF is as follows: albumin (26.3 mg/ml),
138 γ -globulin (8.2 mg/ml), hyaluronic acid (0.82 mg/ml), and phospholipids (0.35 mg/ml), which were
139 diluted in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). Given the potential for fluorescence microscopy, it was
140 essential to stain the protein albumin with fluorescent markers. The staining of albumin was achieved
141 through the use of fluorescein-5-isothiocyanate (FITC).

142
143 *Fig. 3 The surface structure of tested pins and schematic representation of the printing strategy.*
144
145

146 ***Experimental Design and Evaluation of the Results***

147 The experiments were designed to simulate, to some extent, the behaviour of a small human
148 joint, namely the metatarsophalangeal joint of the big toe (1. MTP). In the absence of ISO standards
149 defining the loading and kinematic conditions in this joint, information from available studies were used.
150 The movement of this joint in a healthy condition was described by Durrant et al. [29], while
151 Allan et al. [30] provided additional information on the kinematics of the joint in the sagittal plane. In
152 addition, Al-Munajjed et al. [31] described another important parameter, namely the contact pressure
153 generated in the 1. MTP joint. Based on these findings, the experimental conditions for reciprocal
154 movement were selected as shown in Tab. 1. The entire experiment consisted of a total of 60 cycles.
155 Subsequently, following every 20 cycles, the contact pair was relieved (simulating joint unloading),
156 which lasted for five minutes. The aforementioned interval was also used for the storage of the acquired
157 image records during the measurements.

158 *Tab. 1 Experimental conditions.*

Normal load	Stroke	Speed	Frequency	Number of cycles
1 N	20 mm	20 mm/s	0.5 Hz	60*

* Each experiment included an interruption after each 20 cycles to simulate joint unloading.

159
160 A subsequent challenge that had to be addressed in the experimental design was the orientation
161 of the structures during measurement. Based on the potential for comparison of the resulting data, the
162 orientations were selected as follows: samples with line structures were tested so that the resulting dents
163 (lines) were parallel to the direction of motion. This approach was selected in preference to testing lines
164 perpendicular to the motion, as previous studies had not identified any benefit in doing so, due to the
165 disruption of the lubricating film or even a complete collapse [32] that can be caused by outflow of the
166 lubricant on sides of the groove. In accordance with the aforementioned selection of the line structure,
167 the grid structure was also subjected to a corresponding rule, whereby the axis of the dents was
168 consistently determined and aligned with the orientation of the movement (see Fig. 4).

169 The evaluation of the experiments was based on the methodology presented in the preliminary
170 study [23]. The experiments were evaluated in a single direction of motion, with the friction coefficient

171 obtained from the mean of the filtered values from the entire area (the dead ends of the cycle were not
 172 considered in the evaluation). With regard to the evaluation of the lubrication film thickness and
 173 subsequent experiments conducted using fluorescence microscopy, the midpoint of the aforementioned
 174 one-way motion was identified as the optimal point for analysis as it is not affected by dead ends and
 175 the lubrication film is stable. The resulting values were subsequently plotted in the graphs presented in
 176 the Results and Discussion sections. The evaluation principle is illustrated in Fig. 4. In order to evaluate
 177 the results of the optical observations, custom software [25,33] were employed to obtain precise data
 178 regarding the thickness of the lubricating film and the concentration of albumin protein in the contact
 179 area.

180
 181 *Fig. 4 Experimental design – orientation of samples during experiments (left); Scheme of the experimental*
 182 *evaluation principle (right).*

184 3. Results

185 To ensure sufficient repeatability for each tested sample, all experiments from which the final
 186 graphs for friction and lubrication film thickness were created were repeated three times. In all graphs,
 187 individual samples are distinguished by colour. The colour grey is used to indicate a pin with a
 188 homogeneous surface, blue for a pin with a grid structure and red for a pin with a line structure.
 189 Furthermore, the vertical dashed line represents the load relief phase, as described in the Materials and
 190 Methods section.

191 With regard to the friction coefficient, it can be observed that the value increased from the
 192 beginning of the experiment, but subsequently reached a similar value of approximately 0.43 for the
 193 homogeneous surface and grid structure. In contrast, the stabilisation for the line structure occurred at a

194 value of approximately 0.48. The frictional behaviour of all samples is illustrated in Fig. 5. The most
 195 notable distinction was observed in the second phase of the experiment for the grid structure (20 to 40
 196 cycles), where a considerable decline in the friction coefficient was evident after the unloading phase.
 197 Following a few cycles, the coefficient of friction approached the values of the sample with a
 198 homogeneous surface and followed a similar development and stabilisation trajectory. The experiments
 199 with the line structure exhibited the least significant discrepancies across the repeatability tests,
 200 indicating that this structure may offer the most stable contact pair behaviour. However, the coefficient
 201 of friction was the highest among the other samples.

202
 203 *Fig. 5 CoF for individual samples with shown repeatability (left); comparison of the average values (right).*

205 The results obtained from the observation of the lubrication film thickness using colorimetric
 206 interferometry demonstrated that the lubrication film was disrupted for all samples at a specific stage of
 207 the experiment, typically prior to the end of the initial phase. This finding indicates that the incorporation
 208 of this phase did not negatively impact the formation of the lubrication film at the first sight as the
 209 disruption occurred even before this phase. This resulted in the friction pairs coming into contact with
 210 one another, thereby eliminating the possibility of separating them with the lubrication layer and,
 211 consequently, reducing the crucial parameter – wear rate. The observation indicated that the
 212 implemented unloading phase affected the behaviour of the samples comprising the grid structure, but
 213 not those of the other samples. The samples with a grid structure exhibited an increase in the lubrication

214 film between the initial and second phases of the experiment, resulting in the restoration of the
 215 lubrication film and the desired separation of the friction pairs. However, the lubrication film once again
 216 failed after a few cycles. The second unloading phase had no further effect on the behaviour of the
 217 lubrication film thickness. A comparison of the average values of the film thicknesses revealed
 218 comparable trends for samples with a grid structure and a homogeneous surface, which aligned with the
 219 results of friction. In contrast, samples with a line structure exhibited a notable reduction in film
 220 thickness. However, the observed differences in the average lubrication film thicknesses should be
 221 interpreted with caution, as they varied to some extent across repeatability.

222
 223 *Fig. 6 Evolution of lubrication film thickness for all tested samples with shown repeatability (top); comparison*
 224 *of the average values (middle); images from colorimetric interferometry (bottom).*

225
 226 To reinforce the insights gained from the friction and lubrication film thickness analyses,
 227 fluorescence microscopy was employed to examine the stained protein albumin and its behaviour within
 228 the contact region of the tested samples (see Fig. 7). Significantly overexposed spots (structure dents),

229 where the protein concentration is significantly higher due to their trapping, were excluded from the
 230 evaluation using a threshold so as to avoid a potential bias in the results. In terms of protein concentration
 231 in the contact area, the grid-structured samples exhibited the most favourable results, followed by the
 232 homogeneous samples, and the lowest concentration was observed in the line-structured samples. With
 233 regard to the grid structure, the most notable impact was observed after the unloading phase, where the
 234 protein concentration took several cycles to return to the anticipated level. In the case of the
 235 homogeneous surface, this occurred within two to three cycles. In contrast, no protein increase was
 236 observed in the contact area after unloading phase for the line structure.

237 *Fig. 7 Evolution of contact area coverage by protein albumin during the whole experiment (top) and*
 238 *fluorescence microscopy images for each sample (bottom).*
 239

240
 241 Moreover, the static loaded images of the contact area before and after each phase of the
 242 experiment were compared within the fluorescence microscopy to evaluate the behaviour of the protein
 243 albumin and its capability to maintain within the contact area. It can be observed that the initial phase
 244 represents an outlier, as during this stage of the experiment, there was an increase in albumin

245 concentration within the contact region for the homogeneous surface and grid structure, thereby forming
 246 some kind of layer. Whereas there was a decrease for the line structure. A comparison of the subsequent
 247 phases reveals a similarity in the pattern of the waveforms, with a consistent decline in concentration
 248 throughout the experimental period, when the albumin concentration stabilizes at the end of the
 249 experiment at a similar value to that established at the end of the first phase.

250
 251 *Fig. 8 Coverage of the sensed area (3 times larger in diameter than contact area) by protein albumin in static*
 252 *images before and after the phases of experiment.*

253
 254 The images produced by the profilometer following the experiments indicate that the wear rate was not
 255 significant. As the experiments were conducted over a limited period, only the wear scars were analysed,
 256 as the wear rate would not have provided sufficient insight. It is notable that the samples exhibited
 257 certain differences. The sample with a homogenous surface exhibited the visually most pronounced wear
 258 scar. This sample also exhibited the occurrence of grooves, which were accompanied by areas where
 259 the material was observed to be pushed upwards during the course of the experiment. Only slight
 260 deformation of the contact area was observed for the line structure, while virtually no wear was observed
 261 for the grid structure. Furthermore, the images demonstrate that the created structures exhibit sunken
 262 edges, which eliminates the possibility of any negative influence on the behaviour observed during the
 263 experiments.

264

265 *Fig. 9 Typical wear scars for each sample: homogenous (left), line structure (middle), grid structure (right).*

266

267 **4. Discussion**

268 **General Discussion**

269 The objective of the presented study was to provide a detailed description of the tribological
 270 behaviour observed in three distinct specimens, all of which were manufactured using 3D printing
 271 technology from a Ti6Al4V alloy. The tribological parameters investigated included the friction
 272 coefficient, lubrication film thickness (colorimetric interferometry), development of constituents in
 273 synovial fluid (fluorescence microscopy), and wear. The first sample was produced with a homogeneous
 274 surface. The second and third samples were created with a surface structure produced directly by 3D
 275 printing, with the resulting structures being of a grid and line-based configuration in accordance with
 276 the method of production. The experiments were conducted on the tribometer with a pin-on-plate
 277 configuration utilising a reciprocal movement using a synthetically prepared model synovial fluid as a
 278 lubricant. The kinematic and loading conditions were set in accordance with those employed in our
 279 preliminary study [23], which were as follows: a normal load of 1 N, a stroke of 20 mm, a speed of 20
 280 mm/s, and 60 cycles with an interruption after each 20 cycles to simulate the joint unloading.

281 The results for the friction coefficient exhibited a comparable trend across all tested samples,
 282 which could be characterized by a gradual initial increase and subsequent stabilization at a value around
 283 which it fluctuated. However, a notable difference was observed in the case of the grid structure, where
 284 a significant decline in the coefficient of friction was evident following the initial phase of the

285 experiment, with a reduction from approximately 0.43 to approximately 0.38. The reduction in the
286 coefficient of friction at the beginning of the second experimental phase was presumably associated with
287 an increase in the thickness of the lubrication film and a momentary separation of the friction pairs (see
288 Fig. 6), which occurred following the unloading and reloading between the first and second experimental
289 phases. This phenomenon was not observed in the other samples and could not be attributed to
290 measurement error, as the similar trend was consistent across different samples with the grid structure
291 during the repeatability testing. A number of studies have demonstrated a certain reduction in the
292 coefficient of friction [34,35] following surface texturing. However, this dependence was not observed
293 in the results of the present study, which may be attributed to a number of factors, including the
294 application of different loads, relative velocities and contact materials. This was also demonstrated by
295 Lee [36], who investigated the metal-on-metal contact pair. Following the application of textures, an
296 increase in the friction coefficient was observed.

297 The results obtained from the colorimetric interferometry (see Fig. 6) demonstrate that the
298 lubrication film was disrupted, resulting in direct contact between the friction pairs. The images obtained
299 did not reveal the formation of PAL, even with a sufficiently thick lubricating film for the first few
300 cycles as described by Myant et al. [14]. The typical cluster of proteins in the inlet zone of the contact
301 did not occur, which may be attributed to lower speeds used for the experiments. Fluorescence
302 microscopy revealed that the proteins are capable of forming a layer between the friction pairs. As
303 illustrated in Fig. 7 and 8, protein albumin initially exhibits a tendency to be pushed into the irregularities
304 on the surface of the samples during the initial phase of the experiment. This is followed by the formation
305 of a thin boundary layer between the contact pairs, whereby the proteins adhere and become distributed
306 across the surface. The fluorescence intensity (quantity of proteins in the contact area) at the culmination
307 of each stage is comparable between the homogeneous surface and grid structure, indicating the presence
308 of a stable layer of adhered proteins. Based on the observations made, it was noted that following the
309 unloading and reloading between phases, other proteins entered the contact area. However, they lacked
310 the necessary strength of bonds to maintain their presence in the contact area, and after a few cycles,
311 they were washed out. Moreover, a correlation can be observed between the development of the

312 coefficient of friction and the accumulation of adhered proteins in the contact area. Initially, as the
313 number of proteins increases, the coefficient of friction rises gradually. Subsequently, as the protein
314 concentration in the contact area stabilises, forming a stable thin layer, the coefficient of friction also
315 reaches a steady state. This correlation has been previously demonstrated [37,38], whereby an increase
316 in the quantity of proteins present in the contact area is accompanied by an increase in the coefficient of
317 friction.

318 The graph (see Fig. 10) illustrates the evolution of protein albumin over the course of one half
319 cycle. In order to facilitate analysis, a representative evolution was selected (represented by the 10th
320 cycle of the experiment). The y-axis displays the normalised fluorescence intensity, enabling
321 comparison of the trends across experiments conducted with fluorescence microscopy. Ambient light
322 can significantly impact these experiments, making direct comparison challenging without
323 normalisation. To this end, the initial value was shifted to 0, facilitating the presentation of
324 dimensionless trends within the evaluated experimental area. The analysis is based on the evaluation of
325 fluorescence intensity in the close area around the contact, which serves as an indicator of the presence
326 of protein albumin. The homogeneous surface exhibited a typical non-stable evolution, whereby the
327 clusters of proteins traversed the contact area and were unable to remain present within it. This was due
328 to their inherent ability to adhere to the surface, which enabled them to pass freely through the contact
329 area. In contrast, the structured samples exhibited a distinct behaviour. An improvement was observed
330 for the sample with a grid structure, whereby the quantity of proteins present in the contact area increased
331 from the original value and remained relatively stable throughout the course of a single cycle. However,
332 the amount of protein in the contact area for the sample with a line structure remained below the original
333 value for the entirety of the cycle, indicating that this structure was not optimal in terms of protein
334 retention. Furthermore, it is evident that the quantity of protein albumin present within the contact area
335 is considerably diminished in the case of the line structure. This is evidenced by the markedly reduced
336 intensity of the stream observed in the outlet zone, in comparison to the other samples, where the stream
337 of proteins exiting the contact area is distinctly visible on the right-hand side of the images (see Fig. 10).

338

339 *Fig. 10 Evolution of normalised fluorescence intensity (protein albumin) in the contact area (top) and images*
 340 *from fluorescence microscopy (bottom) for the 10th cycle of the experiment.*

341

342 It was evident that the wear rate of all samples produced via 3D printing technology (see Fig. 9)
 343 had improved from the samples prepared from Ti6Al4V using conventional methods in our preliminary
 344 study [24]. Furthermore, the absence of deep grooves that were observed for these samples indicated a
 345 notable enhancement in the quality of the printed samples. The most significant improvement was
 346 observed in the sample with a grid structure, where it was not even possible to find a wear area on the
 347 samples after the experiments. It was even possible to record released wear particles moving within a
 348 created dimple using colorimetric interferometry during the experiment. This confirmed their ability to
 349 trap these wear particles [39] and prevent them from contributing to secondary wear.

350

351 **Data Repeatability**

352 Based on the findings, it can be clearly observed that repeatability of the results is achievable,
 353 but the results are not perfectly identical, which is phenomenon typical for the biotribological
 354 experiments. This fact may be mainly attributed to the behaviour of the synovial fluid, which is a highly
 355 complex fluid [28] with non-Newtonian behaviour and it comprises components that can potentially
 356 influence its overall behaviour [40] based on the experimental setup and conditions. Another aspect is

357 the fact that the samples were created using 3D printing, where the perfect match of the created structure
358 on the surface (grid or line) was not guaranteed, as some of the expected dents may have been blinded
359 during the production (see Fig. 3). As a result, these differences can lead to slightly different contact
360 areas and contact pressures, which can negatively affect the repeatability. However, if we look at the
361 plots obtained in the Results section, we can see that the values vary slightly across measurements, but
362 the trends are identical. For this reason, repeating each experiment three times was chosen as sufficient
363 to illustrate the repeatability properly.

364

365 **Limitations of the Study**

366 One of the fundamental limitations of the study is the use of glass as a counterpart in the
367 experiments. However, this choice was necessary in order to make observations of the contact area using
368 optical methods, which would not have been possible with a non-transparent material. This approach
369 increased the contact pressure and reduced the contact area in comparison to the real joint replacement,
370 in which the metal material is in contact with the ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE).
371 In numerical terms, this represents an increase from 2.4 MPa to 35.1 MPa based on contact Hertz theory,
372 accompanied by a change in the circular contact area from a diameter of 0.887 mm to 0.233 mm. It is
373 acknowledged that these values may appear disparate; however, in the context of understanding the
374 phenomena occurring within the contact area and conducting fundamental research, they are deemed to
375 be acceptable.

376 A further potential discrepancy may emerge with regard to the dimensions of the contact area
377 and the level of contact pressure, as a consequence of the specific structures present on the surface of
378 the samples. It would be challenging to calculate the same contact pressure and, consequently, contact
379 area size due to the random arrangement of the structures, which would make any such calculation
380 highly unreliable. Accordingly, a methodology was established whereby all samples were evaluated
381 under identical normal force conditions, resulting in minor fluctuations in contact pressure and contact
382 area size due to the distribution of structures. It is also noteworthy that the results of the experiments
383 indicated the development of only protein albumin. This decision was made on the basis of the time-

384 consuming nature of the experiments, given that albumin is the most concentrated protein in the synovial
385 fluid. Moreover, it has been demonstrated [16] that albumin plays a fundamental role in the formation
386 of the lubricating film.

387

388 *5. Conclusions*

389 The utilisation of 3D printing technology permitted the production of samples with a surface
390 structure that could be potentially implemented in the friction surfaces of human joint replacements. The
391 selected manufacturing method proved effective, demonstrating that only a finishing
392 operation (polishing) was necessary to produce a surface that appears optimal. The findings indicated
393 that the samples created with a 3D-printed structure did not exhibit any negative effects on tribological
394 behaviour. Furthermore, a reduction in wear was observed in the structured samples. Also, the grid
395 structure demonstrated an increase in the amount of proteins present in the contact area, which may
396 contribute to the formation of a more durable and stable lubrication film. The main disadvantage of the
397 structures produced is that they are of a larger scale and more widely spaced than would be optimal for
398 the intended application. This is reflected in the results obtained, which demonstrate that it was not
399 possible to sufficiently influence the lubrication capabilities of the friction pair under test in terms of
400 increasing or preventing lubrication film failure.

401 The main conclusions of the article are summarised in the following bullet points:

- 402 • The 3D printed samples with a grid structure exhibited the most promising results in terms of their
403 potential applicability as a friction surface for human artificial joints.
 - 404 ○ These samples exhibited similar friction values to the sample with a homogenous surface.
 - 405 ○ They displayed the unique ability to restore the lubrication film after the unloading phase of
406 the experiment, which was not observed in the other samples.
 - 407 ○ These samples showed the highest presence and stable evolution of protein albumin in the
408 contact area, with no decrease but rather an increase during the cycle.
- 409 • Based on the results, it is evident that further refinement of the created structures is necessary,
410 particularly with regard to their proximity and regularity.

411 Nevertheless, this production process appears to be appropriate and should be subjected to further
412 investigation, as these findings suggest that these surfaces could be employed in the manufacture of joint
413 replacements after optimisation of structures. The primary objective is to establish more appropriate
414 printing parameters or identify an alternative 3D printing method that will facilitate a closer alignment
415 with the desired structures, as well as ensure greater regularity. This might be followed by the application
416 of coatings to the resulting surfaces. This approach may prove an effective means of reducing wear, as
417 it has already demonstrated its potential in other studies. Moreover, the samples will be subjected to a
418 long-term wear experimental investigation in order to obtain information regarding their durability.

419

420 ***Credit authorship contribution statement***

421 L. Odehnal, M. Ranuša, and M. Vrbka conceived the idea. L. Odehnal and M. Ranuša designed the
422 experiments. M. Malý designed the 3D printing parameters and produced the test samples. L. Odehnal
423 performed the experiments and analysed the data. L. Odehnal wrote the original draft of the manuscript.
424 M. Ranuša, M. Malý, M. Vrbka revised the manuscript. M. Vrbka and M. Hartl administrated the
425 projects and secured the funding. D. Koutný and I. Křupka supervised the study.

426

427 ***Declaration of Competing Interest***

428 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships
429 that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. The authors declare that they have
430 no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence
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433 ***Data Availability Statement***

434 The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository Zenodo at
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444

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